

A Review On Herbal Drug *Withania Coagulans*

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ABSTRACT:

In Ayurveda, the usage of *Withaniacoagulans*, a plant from the solanaceae family, has been emphasised. We have discussed the chemical constituents, morphology, and pharmacological characteristics of *W. coagulans*. [1] A valuable medicinal plant called *withaniacoagulans* (Family: Solanaceae) has been used to treat a variety of health issues, including aberrant cell growth, wasting diseases, neural and physical issues, diabetes mellitus, sleeplessness, and acute and chronic hepatic conditions. Due to the presence of withanolides, an active component in it, it has been reported to have diuretic, anti-inflammatory, anti-fungal, anti-bacterial, hypoglycemic, cardio-protective, hepato-protective, anti-oxidative, and anti-mutagenic qualities. Numerous studies have shown different *W. coagulans* sections and their dynamic ingredients have a wide range of pharmacological and therapeutic capabilities, making them potential novel medication therapies for a variety of disorders [5]

KEYWORDS: Antidiabetic, Hypoglycemic, Solanaceae, steroidal lactones, withanolides, Ayurvedic properties

INTRODUCTION: Since ancient times, people have used herbal plants to cure and treat a variety of illnesses. Ayurvedic medicine is broadly used due to its low incidence of adverse effects and wide range of benefits [4] There are two species of *Withania*, one is *W. somnifera* and the other is *W. coagulans*, which are distributed in east of the Mediterranean region spreading to South Asia. It is found in many parts of India and our neighbouring country Pakistan. The fruits and leaves of *W. Coagulans* plant are employed as a coagulant, it is also called as "vegetable rennet" or "Indian cheese maker". The husk and pulp of berries, which contain an enzyme known as withanin that has milk-coagulating activity, are thought to be responsible for the fruits' ability to cause milk to coagulate. Among twenty-three identified species of genus *Withania*, only two *W. coagulans* and *W. somnifera*, have economic significance. The healing properties of the plant are attributed to steroid derivative compounds "Withanolides". There are several withanolides such as coagulanolide, withacoagulin, coagulin F, and coagulin G present in the whole plant.

MICROSCOPIC CHARACTERISTICS:

The transverse cut of the fruit reveals a single layer called the exocarp, whereas the mesocarp displays a large zone of parenchymatous cells with strong shows the pedicel and calyx of a *Withaniacoagulans* fruit under a microscope cellular thickening. [8] While the endocarp and exocarp are comparable, there are certain locations where the cell walls have flattened and collapsed. Transverse sections of the seeds reveal a single layer of epidermis followed by a layer of sub-epidermal cells with extremely flattened, thin walls. There is a layer of densely lignified palisade-like cells with a small lumen beneath

the subepidermis. The inner epidermis of the seed coat is made up of one to two layers of parenchymatous cells with thin walls, some of which are collapsed and exhibit hyaline-like structure.[9]

NUTRITION PROFILE :

The berries of the *W. coagulans* are composed of milk coagulating enzymes, two esterase, free amino acids, and essential oil. Proline, tyrosine, valine, hydroxyproline, glycine, cysteine, asparagine, glutamic, and aspartic acids are the main amino acids that are present in the plant. Major fatty acids include arachidonic acid, stearic acid, palmitic acid, linoleic and oleic acids [3]. Furthermore, n-octatriacont-17-enoic acid, geranil-10-olyl dihydrocinnamate (aromatic ester), and geranil-8-oiic acid-10-olyl salicyloxy-2-O-β-D-glucufuranosyl-(6''→1''')-O-β-D-glucufuranosyl-6'''-n-octadec-9''',11'''''' dienoate(monoterpenic benzyl glucoside) in consort with two already identified fatty acids named as n-dotriacont-21-enoic acid and n-tetratriacontanoic acid were characterized in berries [11]. Similarly, research also detected twenty constituents in the essential oil of the *W. coagulans* fruit including sesquiterpenes (54%)and esters (21.50%) as dominant compounds followed by the presence of fatty acids (5.5%) such as nonanoic acid, hexanoic acid, methyl ester of hexadecanoic acid, methyl ester of nondecanoic acid, methyl esters of 8,11-octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester of 9-octadecenoic acid, and ethyl ester of linoleic acid, alkanes (9.11%), and the aldehydes (0.32%) in smaller percentage [12]. The un-saponifiable matter of the plant seed is composed of triacontane as well as β-sitosterol and dihydrostigmasterol [13]. In addition, it was reported that seeds are composed of approximately 12–14% of oil. The presence of free sugar (17.8%) in the form of D-galactose and D-arabinose (1:1) in a de-fatted meal of the *W. coagulans* seeds was also elucidated with maltose present in trace amounts [10]. Higher percentages of β-sitosterol, as well as linoleic acid, were also found and reported for the hypo-cholesterolemic effect of corn oil in combination with *W. coagulans* [15,14].

Table : Mineral composition of *W.coagulans*

Minerals(mg/kg)	
Macro-Minerals	
Calcium	9260
Magnesium	35,280
Potassium	2450
Sodium	125
Micro -Minerals	
Iron	98.8
Copper	2.2
Zinc	40.2
Chromium	0.6
Cadmium	1.4
Lead	1.9
Nickel	1.8

PICTURE:

ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY OF *W.COAGULANS* DUNAL

SYNONYM:

English – Indian cheese maker, vegetable rennet

Hindi – Punirdodi, Paneer phool

Sanskrit – Rishyagandha

Taxonomical classification:

Kingdom: Plantae, Plants;

Subkingdom: Tracheobionta, Vascular plants;

Division: Angiosperms

Class: Dicotyledons

Order: Tubiflorae

Family: Solanaceae

Genus: *Withania*

Species: *Withaniacoagulans*Dunal

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS:

Active Ingredient	Structure	Molecular formula	Location	Pharmacological Importance
Withanolide (steroidal lactones)		22-hydroxyergostan-26-oic acid-26,22-lactone	Roots and Leaves	It is an important hormonal precursor, it can convert into human physiological hormones when the body requires.
Withaferin A		4β,27-dihydroxy-1-oxo-5β,6β-epoxywitha-2-24-dienolide	Root	It has an antibiotic and anti-tumor property.
Withanolide A		C ₂₈ H ₃₈ O ₆	Roots and Leaves	Prevent neurodegeneration, Anticancer agent
Withanolide D		C ₂₈ H ₃₈ O ₆	Root	Significant antitumor and radiosensitizing withanolides

PROPERTIES:**1. Anti-inflammatory Activity:**

Budhiraja et al. investigated the anti-inflammatory efficacy of a withanolide derived from *W. coagulans*, which demonstrated notable effects on sub-acute inflammation in experimental rats. The CNS was not affected by withanolide in any way. In a carrageenin-induced rat paw oedema model, the hydro alcoholic extract of the berries of *W. coagulans* significantly reduced inflammatory activity. [

2. Antidiabetic & Anti-oxidant Activity:

The fruits of *W. coagulans* have an aqueous extract that has been shown to have hypoglycemic action in both normal and streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats (1g/kg; po; 7 days). The high levels of blood glucose, lipid peroxidation (LPO), and cholesterol in diabetic rats were dramatically lowered by the aqueous extract. Additionally, it demonstrated free radical scavenging activity in a DPPH-based in-vitro system. It is common knowledge that insulin stimulates the uptake of glucose by tissues and cells in the periphery. In an isolated rat hemidiaphragm, an aqueous extract of the fruits of this plant demonstrated considerable glucose utilisation.

3. Wound healing Activity:

Streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats received the hydroalcoholic fraction of the methanolic extract of *W. coagulans* in the form of a 10% weight-per-weight ointment topically and at a dose of 500 mg/kg body weight orally. Topical (10% w/w ointment) and oral (500 mg/kg body weight, p.o.) administration of the hydroalcoholic fraction both significantly increased the rate of wound contraction as compared to diabetic controls.

4. Antifungal Activity:

Two new withanolides, 14,15-epoxywithanolide I [(20S,22R) 17-, 20-dihydroxy-14,15-epoxy-1-oxowitha-3,5,24-trienolide] and 17-hydroxywithanolide K (20S, 22R) 14-,17-, 20-trihydroxy-1-oxowitha-2,5,24-trien-olide, were isolated from ethanolic extract of the whole plant.

5. Antibacteria & Antihelmintic Activity:

It has been discovered that the volatile oil from the alcoholic extract of *W. coagulans*' fruits possesses antihelmintic and antibacterial properties against *S. aureus* and *Vibrio cholera*.

6. Antitumor Activity :

When withaferin A was tested in-vitro against cells originating from human carcinoma of the nasopharynx (KB), it significantly inhibited the growth of tumours. The RNA production of Sarcoma-180 ascites tumour cells was suppressed by withaferin A. Within 30 minutes of incubation, it demonstrated a greater than 50% suppression of RNA synthesis at 40 g/ml. It prevented Sarcoma-180 cells from producing protein. Withaferin A prevented these cells' transcription and translation processes in this way. After a 2-hour.

7. Diuretic effect:

With a few minor adjustments and using furosemide as a reference drug, the in vivo Lipschitz test paradigm was used to examine the diuretic efficacy of the aqueous extract of *W. coagulans* fruit. When compared to controls, the results showed a substantial increase in urine volume of 79.12% and 71.02% at doses of 500 mg/kg and 750 mg/kg body weight, respectively. Both dosages resulted in higher urinary electrolyte excretions than the control.

CONCLUSION:

Due to their lack of adverse effects compared to synthetic pharmaceuticals, the usage of herbal drugs is growing globally. The medicinal potential of different plants is claimed by Ayurveda. There are two species of *Withania* in India: *W. somnifera* and *W. coagulans*. Due to the presence of withanolides, *W. coagulans* has a great deal of medicinal potential and has been used as a treatment for many different conditions. Esterases, free amino acids, fatty acids, and essential oils are also present in it. Numerous pharmacological studies have revealed that *W. coagulans* has medicinal qualities including hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, hypoglycemic, cardioprotective, central nervous system depressant, free radical scavenging, antimicrobial, immunomodulation, antitumor, and cytotoxic activities. The variety of biological activities reported for the extracts, fractions and withanolides separated from *W. coagulans* provide promising evidence for future research. Future studies are required to discover the mechanisms of action of compounds separated from *W. coagulans* in higher animals to confirm their protective activity and safety. Rudimentary extracts from different parts of the plant especially from the fruit have significant medicinal potential.

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